

1. Theoretical Foundation

This section introduces some of the key concepts necessary for understanding the research outlined in this paper. It provides information on the MPS.BR model and the Requirements Engineering process within MPS.BR, as well as guidelines for using the PBB method.

1.1. MPS.BR (Brazilian Software Process Improvement)

According to (2024), the Brazilian Software Process Improvement (MPS.BR) program began in 2003 with the support of the Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI). The program aims to improve software development, services, and human resource management practices in the ICT (Information and Communication Technology) industry. The objective of the program is to increase the competitiveness of organizations by improving their processes.

MPS.BR focuses on process management, indicating what the organization must do to achieve the model's expected results, without detailing step-by-step tasks. The model presents maturity levels ranging from G to A, with requirements becoming more stringent as the level increases. Each maturity level comprises a set of processes (the areas of software engineering) with expected results (the requirements that a company must meet to achieve a process's objective).

According to SOFTEX (2024), MPS models are aligned with the main international approaches to define, evaluate, and improve processes. MPS.BR comprises a set of guides in the form of documents, such as: The MPS General Software Guide (MR-MPS-SW), the MPS General Services Guide (MR-MPS-SV), the MPS General Human Resources Management Guide (MR-MPS-RH), and the Assessment Guide (MA-MPS).

In this study, the MPS General Software Guide (MR-MPS-SW) is used, which aims to implement software engineering principles in a way that is appropriate for the context of companies, in accordance with international approaches for defining, evaluating, and improving software processes. Likewise, in this work, the Requirements Engineering process is used, which establishes the process of defining software requirements, which involves eliciting, modeling, and analyzing. 'The purpose of the Requirements Engineering process is to define, manage, and maintain current stakeholder and product requirements, ensuring that inconsistencies between requirements, plans, and work products are identified and addressed' (SOFTEX, 2024).

An expected result is defined as the objectives that an organization must achieve when implementing a process according to the models defined by MPS.BR. These results are specific and measurable, ensuring that the processes are executed as planned, producing the expected benefits. According to SOFTEX (2024), the expected results of

the Requirements Engineering process are:

- REQ 1 - The needs, expectations, and constraints of the stakeholders in relation to the product and its interfaces are identified, and the requirements are confirmed. In this expected result, initial contact is made with the customer and their needs are identified. Based on these needs, the product's features are defined. Customer expectations generally relate to product quality and performance and reflect the desired ideal scenario. Constraints refer to limitations imposed by the solution, such as compatibility with specific operating systems,
- REQ 2 - Requirements are specified, prioritized, refined, and allocated for implementation, and kept up to date, based on the needs, expectations, and constraints identified in REQ 1. This involves translating the customer's needs into technical terms and covers the definition, prioritization, refinement, allocation, and maintenance of requirements. This includes specifying operational concepts, scenarios, and internal and external interfaces. An interface is the means by which communication occurs between two distinct parts of a system that cannot connect directly. Operational concepts are linked to the prototyping of requirements and can be demonstrated using a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) diagram illustrating how the requirement is operationalized. A scenario is a sequence of events that can occur during use of the product,
- REQ 3 - The technical team commits to implementing the requirements. This is evidenced by meeting minutes, emails, or other appropriate documentation methods,
- REQ 4 - Bidirectional traceability is established and maintained between project requirements, activities, and work products. A system must be set up to track the relationship between requirements and work products in a software project. This ensures that each requirement is linked to the corresponding work products and vice versa. This process is crucial for assessing the impact of changes to requirements, managing changes, ensuring quality, and facilitating audits,
- REQ 5 - Plans, activities, and related work products are reviewed to identify and address inconsistencies in relation to the defined requirements. It is essential to align all the elements of the project with these requirements by performing reviews, monitoring the project, and implementing corrective actions as necessary. When changes are made to the requirements, it is necessary to verify that the other project work products are consistent with these changes,
- REQ 6 - Requirements are understood and analyzed to ensure they are necessary and sufficient, and to balance the needs of stakeholders with existing constraints. This expected result emphasizes the importance of understanding and analyzing requirements to ensure that they are clear, necessary, and sufficient, and that the needs of stakeholders are balanced with existing constraints. Evidence must be presented to prove these points. Balancing involves reviewing, improving, and evolving the product, creating a new version each time this procedure is executed, and generating a history,
- REQ 7 - Requirements are validated to ensure that they meet the customer's needs

and that the project team and stakeholders share a common understanding of them. This expected result requires a more specific and descriptive validation method, such as use case analysis or prototyping.

1.2. PBB (Product Backlog Building)

According to Aguiar and Caroli (2022), Scrum is the most widely used agile framework for product development. 'However, the Scrum framework does not define how to build the backlog. This is why PBB complements Scrum, helping teams develop an effective Product Backlog'.

According to Aguiar and Caroli (2022), there are three fundamental aspects to consider when talking about the backlog:

- The product backlog is an ordered and emergent list of what is needed to improve the product,
- The backlog is the only source of work performed by the Scrum team,
- The Product Owner is responsible for effectively managing the backlog.

According to Aguiar and Caroli (2022), the main objective of Product Backlog Building (PBB) is to help build and refine the Product Backlog collaboratively. This method promotes a shared understanding of the product among everyone involved and prepares the backlog for agile and effective teamwork, using the PBB Canvas as a facilitation tool. 'PBB clarifies and prioritizes user stories and items to be added to the Scrum team's backlog'.

According to Aguiar and Caroli (2022), the benefits of the PBB method include:

- It helps build and refine a backlog in an effective and collaborative way,
- It builds a shared understanding of the customer's business, facilitating the discovery and understanding of the product,
- It describes the user's experience with the product,
- It facilitates the discovery and writing of the user story,
- It defines a minimum of alignment and initial planning,
- It produces a Product Backlog fully aligned with the customer's needs.

'The PBB method uses Canvas as a facilitation tool. It provides a simple, easy-to-understand, and process that makes it easier to understand the customer's needs and develop the product backlog' (Aguiar & Caroli, 2022).

Aguiar and Caroli (2022) state that building a backlog in PBB should follow this flow:

- Contextualize the Product: It is essential to clarify and understand what the product is, identify the problems and challenges that need to be addressed, and highlight expectations. To achieve this, the product name and the expectations and problems of the stakeholders must be defined,
- Describe the personas: 'A persona represents a product user, so this description

should not only speak about their role but also about their needs and objectives. This creates a realistic representation of users, helping the team describe features from the point of view of those who will use the product'. In Canvas, the persona is listed alongside their activities,

- Understand the features: 'A feature is the description of an action or interaction of a user with the product. For example, requesting shared transport, consulting a detailed statement, or making an online purchase. The description of the feature should be as simple as possible'. In PBB Canvas, each feature should be described with a brief explanation, highlighting the 'problems' it aims to solve and the benefits' it provides,
- Identify the PBIs: Aguiar and Caroli (2022) state that Product Backlog Items (PBIs) are elements of the Product Backlog that represent development work to improve the product and meet the needs of customers and stakeholders. After describing the features and listing their respective problems and benefits, it can identify the PBIs by dividing the features into smaller, more precise items. Asking what the first, second, and subsequent work items are can help to write the PBIs.

The process responsible for identifying and creating a PBI is called the 'Steps Map'. 'In PBB, features are broken down into PBIs using the Steps Map technique, which helps to break a feature down into small steps, each of which becomes a PBI' (Aguiar & Caroli, 2022).

The Steps Map is applied in two stages: First, the step-by-step process of the feature is defined, resulting in a workflow. For example, if the feature were 'Register Book', what would the first step be? The second stage involves evolving each step with questions, comments, and ideas to complete each step of the feature. Re-evaluate each one. A question can eliminate an unnecessary step, a comment can improve a useful step, and an idea can generate a new step.

Ultimately, following the sequence of steps on the PBB Canvas, the list of PBIs will be obtained — this is the list that contains the items in the Product Backlog.

Each PBI describes a user action in the product. Aguiar and Caroli (2022) explain that the actions are written in text form to provide context and uniquely identify an item. The authors also suggest that PBIs should be written in the ARO model. 'Development work to improve the product by meeting the needs of the customer or stakeholders'. Thus, in the ARO model, each PBI is described as an action, result, and object.

According to Schwaber and Shuterland (2020), the product backlog is an ordered and continuously updated list of what is needed to improve the product. Therefore, a 'ordered and emerging' product backlog is a prioritized and continuously updated list of product requirements.

Every project requires that work items be prioritized. This is particularly important for

Agile teams, as they perform incremental deliveries. Prioritizing work items determines the order in which they will be developed.

According to Aguiar and Caroli (2022), COORG is the PBB prioritization technique responsible for prioritizing PBIs. It is an acronym for classify, order, and organize. COORG helps the team prioritize the backlog with the aim of planning and aligning workflow and/or the next sprints.

COORG involves several steps: (i) Classify, the first step is to classify each PBI by establishing criteria and classification scales with the team according to the product context. The authors state that it is crucial to align and decide on these criteria before classifying PBIs. (ii) Order, the second step is to order the features in a logical sequence, like a narrative, moving their respective PBIs below them. (iii) Organize, the third and final step is to organize the PBIs of each feature from top to bottom by priority. Then, place the PBIs with the highest score in the first row and so on in descending order.

Aguiar and Caroli (2022) state that the results of COORG activities should not be definitive. They are an initial prioritization that can and should be updated as the backlog evolves and new items emerge. The 'PBB Canvas' tool provides a visual representation of the entire product design, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PBB Canvas.

2. Concepts for PBB-M

To gain a good understanding of the PBB-M implementation guidelines, it is necessary to clarify some concepts beforehand. These are:

- PBB-M Facilitator: As in PBB, the PBB-M Facilitator is responsible for leading the PBB session, ensuring active team participation, promoting collaboration, and

ensuring the Product Backlog is efficiently built and aligned with the team's objectives,

- PBB-M Session: Similar to PBB, the PBB-M Session is a structured meeting in which the team collaborates to define and refine the Product Backlog visually and interactively using the PBB-M Canvas,
- PBB-M Canvas: A visual tool that helps the team refine and structure the Product Backlog, adapted to meet the MPS.BR Requirements Engineering process requirements,
- Product Owner (PO): The PO is responsible for maximizing the value of the product by managing the Product Backlog and ensuring that the items are well defined, prioritized, and aligned with business and stakeholder needs. They act as a 'bridge' between the development team and stakeholders, ensuring that the delivered product generates the greatest possible value,
- Developer: The role responsible for developing the product increment. Developers are professionals with diverse skills who work collaboratively to deliver continuous value throughout the project,
- Development Team: It is made up of professionals responsible for creating the product increment during the Sprint. The team is cross-functional and self-organizing, ensuring that all necessary development activities are completed,
- Planning Poker: A collaborative estimation technique used to define the effort required to develop a PBI. Team members assign complexity points based on a set of cards to reach a consensus on the level of effort involved,
- Sprint: A development cycle lasting between one and four weeks in which the team works to deliver a potentially usable product increment,
- Increment: Functional delivery of the product at the end of a sprint. Each increment builds on the previous ones, ensuring that the product evolves continuously and remains usable.

3. Application of the PBB and PBB-M Activities in the Context

3.1. Contextualizing the Product

The product was given the simple and direct name 'Online Library', which clearly conveys its purpose. This marks the beginning of the implementation of PBB-M.

One of the main identified problems was the lack of clear reports on library usage, which hinders administrative decision-making and efficient resource allocation.

One of the expectations set was that the system would generate clear and understandable reports, allowing efficient visual analysis of library usage statistics.

One of the constraints identified for the Online Library was that the system would be developed as a web application to ensure compatibility with different devices and facilitate remote access.

Figure 2 shows the contextualized PBB-M Canvas, with the fields Product Name, Problems, Expectations, and Constraints filled in.

Figure 2. PBB-M Canvas filled.

3.2. Defining Personas

In the Online Library, one of the personas identified was the Reader: a library user who performs activities such as reading, borrowing, renewing loans, and consulting the book collection.

When applying the PBB-M methodology, the following information was collected:

- What does he do today? The Reader needs to go to the library in person to renew the loan of a book,
- What does he expect from the product? The Reader would like to be able to access the online catalog to search for, reserve, and renew books remotely, without having to travel.

Figure 2 illustrates the documentation of the Reader and Librarian personas on the PBB-M Canvas, showing how their current activities relate to their expectations of the solution.

3.3. Defining Features

The Reader persona searches for books. Based on this action, the corresponding functionality is to consult the online book catalog. Figure 2 shows the features of the Reader and Librarian personas, listed on the PBB-M Canvas.

3.4. Creating PBIs

A PBI for the 'Consult online book catalog' feature would be 'Access the book search interface'. This represents a lower-level user action, a detail of the feature.

- Define the feature step by step. Applying step 1 of the Steps Map, what actions does the user need to perform to consult the catalog for the feature 'Consult online book catalog'? What is the first step? And the next ones? The actions and steps of the persona are listed as follows: (i) access the search interface; (ii) configure search criteria; (iii) start a search; (iv) view search results; (v) view book details. Once the actions have been mapped, they must be described in the ARO model to provide context and uniquely identify each item. The persona actions are described in the ARO model as follows: (i) Access the book search interface, (ii) Enter search criteria in the catalog, (iii) Perform the search in the catalog, (iv) Display the search results in the catalog, (v) Display the details of a selected book,
- Develop each step with questions, comments, and ideas. To apply the second step of the Steps Map, we can apply the following reflections to the 'Access the search interface' step: Questions, (i) Will access to the search interface be exclusive to logged-in users, or will it be publicly available? (ii) Will the search interface be accessed directly from the main menu or from a specific homepage? Comments, (i) The search interface must be easily accessible from the system's main menu, (ii) We must ensure consistency in design with other pages to facilitate navigation. Ideas, (i) Add quick shortcuts to the search interface on the home page. (ii) Create a simple tutorial for new users on how to use the search interface.

At the end of steps 1 and 2, each step in the workflow represents a backlog item or PBI:

- PBI1: Access (Action) the interface (Result) of book search (Object),
- PBI2: Enter the search criteria in the catalog,
- PBI3: Perform the search in the book catalog,
- PBI4: Display the search results in the catalog,
- PBI5: Display the details of a selected book.

Figure 3 illustrates the PBIs in the ARO model in the PBB-M Canvas below their respective features. Once the Steps Map is finished, the PBI Cards can be filled in with information on each PBI, bearing in mind that they have already been refined at this point. Figure 3 illustrates the completed PBI9.

Feature: Managing administrative reports		
ID: 9	PBI: Export generated report to PDF and Excel formats	Depends on: 8
Responsible: Sergio Sousa	Priority: 7	Impacts on: 6
Description: Allow the export of reports generated in the system to PDF and Excel formats, with a button in the reports interface, respecting applied filters and ensuring consistency in design and layout according to the system's visual standard.		
BDD: Scenario 1: Export report to PDF with filters applied Given that the user has generated a report with filters when user clicks on the "Export PDF" button then the system should generate and make available the report in PDF format, applying the configured filters. Scenario 2: Export report to Excel with filters applied		
Related Tasks: 9.1 Add "Export PDF" button to the reporting interface. 9.2 Implement PDF generation feature based on filtered data. 9.3 Test the layout and visual consistency of the exported report. 9.4 Export the generated report to Excel format		
Terter: Jaqueline Cunha		Date: / /
Status: In Progress	Beginning: / /	End: / /

Figure 3. PBI Card filled.

It is worth noting that the Steps Map can be applied to the construction of the Technical PBI, with some reservations. The PBI name must clearly represent its technical nature without having to follow the ARO model format. The description must include technical details such as specifications and configurations. In the BDD field, the scenarios must ensure the validation of integrations, external interfaces, and other technical aspects. Figure 4 shows the completed Technical PBI 12.

Feature: Looking the online book catalog		
ID: 12	PBI: ISBN API integration	Depends on: 2
Responsible:	Priority:	Impacts on: 1
Description: Implement integration with an ISBN API (such as Google Books, Open Library or other) to automate obtaining complete bibliographic information about books in the system, reducing manual work and improving the efficiency of collection management.		
BDD: Scenario 1: Search book data by ISBN Given: A valid ISBN when: The user types the ISBN into the system and clicks search. then: The system searches the chosen API and returns the book information (title, author, etc.).		
Related Tasks: 12.1 Search for the chosen API configuration 12.2 Adjust the database to store the new data. 12.3 Create an interface to search by ISBN		
Terter:		Date: / /
Status:	Beginning: / /	End: / /

Figure 4. Technical PBI Card filled.

Initial prototypes (low-level prototypes) can be created after filling out the PBI Cards. A prototype can represent a feature, a PBI, or both. Figure 5 shows the prototype for PBI 1.

Figure 5. PBI1 Prototype.

Once the PBI Cards have been completed, the PBB-M Facilitator can end the session. To do so, the version, evaluation, participants, and date fields must be completed, as shown in Figure 2.

3.5. Prioritizing PBIs

The 'Export generated report to PDF and Excel formats' feature in PBI is one of the main interfaces of the system for the Librarian and Reader personas. Both personas use it to generate reports containing system information and export this information to PDF or Excel formats.

Therefore, this feature will be used more than once a day, so the frequency of use will be set to 5. This PBI's business value will be 2 (medium) as it is an important feature for all personas. This is justified given that the objective of the system is to optimize book consultation, loans, and renewals. Therefore, the priority of this PBI is calculated as follows: $Priority = 5 + 2 = 7$.

Enter the value 7 in the 'Priority' field on the PBI Card, as shown in Figure 3. Note that the criteria and scales may vary and must be defined jointly by the team.

When prioritizing all PBIs, classify and organize them in the PBB-M Canvas as shown in Figure 6. To convert the PBB-M Canvas into an ordered list of tasks, follow the matrix in Figure 6 from left to right and top to bottom.

Figure 6. PBB-M Canvas classified and ordered.

3.6. Sprint Planning

Assuming the sprint goal is to implement the 'Managing administrative reports' feature. One of the priority product backlog items (PBIs) would be 'PBI 9: Export generated reports to PDF and Excel formats'. This can be broken down into the following tasks: 'Add an Export PDF button to the reporting interface', 'Implement a PDF generation feature based on filtered data', 'Test the layout and visual consistency of the exported report', and 'Export the generated report to Excel format'. Once the estimates and assignments have been defined, complete the 'Responsible' field as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

3.7. Daily Scrum

During the review ceremony (which will be described in the next topic), an inconsistency was identified in 'PBI 9: Export generated report to PDF and Excel formats'. In addition to the requirement to export to PDF, stakeholders requested the ability to export the report in Excel format.

To address this inconsistency, the correction task '9.4 Export the generated report to Excel format' was created, as illustrated in Figure 3. During the Daily Scrum, the person responsible for the task must report on its progress, updating the status field as necessary. Monitoring of this corrective action will continue daily until the issue is fully resolved and validated by the team.

3.8. Review

During the presentation of 'PBI 9: Export generated report to PDF and Excel formats' in

the review stage, the team identified that the implemented criteria did not fully meet the needs of the stakeholders. Therefore, it was necessary to include the option to export to Excel, as requested.

If an inconsistency occurs, the first step is to document it by creating a new task to correct PBI 9. This can be recorded using an adapted PBI Card, as shown in Figure 3. The 'Related Tasks' field of PBI 9 must also be updated to reflect this correction, as shown in Figure 4. This task must include:

- A description of the new export,
- The impact on other parts of the system that use this functionality,
- A list of related items that need to be reviewed (PBIs, documentation, schedule, etc.),
- An estimated time required to correct and update the PBI Card.

After creating the task, the PBI 9 correction must be assigned to a responsible person, and progress must be monitored during the Daily Scrum to ensure that the correction is completed within the defined deadline.

Finally, validate that the implemented correction is in accordance with the updated requirement. Confirm with stakeholders that the new export format meets expectations and is aligned with project requirements.

3.9. Updating Backlog

The practical application of these activities in the Online Library can be understood by following the steps detailed in this section. The creation and prioritization of PBIs, and Sprint Planning, are covered in subsections 3.4, 3.5, and 3.6, respectively. These subsections describe the adopted criteria and how each activity was executed within the project.

As these activities are subject to continuous refinement, the Product Owner (PO) and stakeholders can perform the creation and prioritization of PBIs in a PBI-M session before Sprint Planning at each Sprint Planning. This ensures that, by the end of the session, the PBIs are clear, necessary and prioritized.

At the end of Sprint Planning, with the development team's participation, the PBIs' granularity will be defined appropriately, ensuring they are ready for implementation. Remember to always fill in the PBB-M Canvas Version field with each update.